

A System for Monitoring Children with Suspected Cardiac Arrhythmias Technical Optimizations and Evaluation

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Abstract— Children with cardiac arrhythmias constitute one of the most difficult problems in cardiology both in terms of diagnosis and management. In such cases continuous monitoring of ECG vital signs and environmental conditions can significantly improve the identification of a possible arrhythmia. In this study we present a system which enables the continuous monitoring of children with suspected cardiac arrhythmias. The system is able to carry out real-time acquisition and transmission of ECG signals, and facilitate an alarm scheme able to identify possible arrhythmias so as to notify the on-call doctor and the relatives of the child that an event may be happening. In-house monitoring of a child is performed using a sensor network able to record and transmit ECG and the living conditions, while outside the house, monitoring is performed through a GPRS/UMTS enabled device. The transmitted information can be accessed through a web based platform which facilitates a basic electronic patient record module and continuous display of monitoring information of the patient. This paper presents the technical tests, optimization and hardware changes applied in order to improve the system when used for the in-house monitoring of children.

Keywords— Mobile health, sensor networks, emergency monitoring, children arrhythmias.

I. INTRODUCTION

Telemedicine has been used for many years in order to improve health care provision or for patient monitoring solutions. Several issues such as the computational capability, size of the devices, power efficiency and cost have been limiting the availability of devices and services to a few special cases [1], [2]. Recent advancements in communications and computer systems can help us develop general-purpose systems that are more efficient, much smaller and at lower costs.

In this study, we will focus on the continuous monitoring of children with suspected cardiac arrhythmias. Arrhythmia is one of the most difficult problems in Cardiology both in terms of diagnosis and management. The problem is particularly pronounced in Pediatric Cardiology because of

Fig.1. Overall system Architecture © IEEE 2007 [6]

the variety of etiologies and the difficulty that the children are having in trying to communicate their symptoms. For example in the case of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, it is known that children are at higher risk for arrhythmias and sudden death than adults. In most of the cases an ECG tracing is required and this is sufficient for an accurate diagnosis, whereas in some cases, a more sophisticated modality is required [1], [3].

As an example, a relatively recently recognized rare form of cardiomyopathy, the Isolated Noncompaction of the Left Ventricle (NCLV), poses new challenges. A subset of patients with this disease are especially prone to arrhythmia and sudden death. Current testing with the Holter monitor has proved insufficient because it is limited to 24 or 48 hours of recording during which the patient may be asymptomatic. Some of these children are high risk for sudden death and at the same time it is very difficult to decide for the proper treatment, making their ECG monitoring a very important task [1], [4].

In order to monitor these children sufficiently we need a noninvasive or minimally invasive way to record the ECG for extended periods of time and at the same time perform automatic analysis continuously or at frequent intervals. Work presented here concerns the technical changes carried

Fig.2 UML – sequence diagram of the actions performed during the in-house case © IEEE 2007 [6]

out in order to improve the quality of the system when used in the subjects house. The software design and initial development have already being presented in [6], [7]. The work is a significant extension over our earlier telemedicine work in real-time ambulatory monitoring systems [5].

II. METHODOLOGY

In general the problem has been divided into two cases. The first one, called “In-house case” where the subject is located in his/her house. While for the second, called “Moving patient case” where the subject might be located anywhere else. Our goal is the continuous 24 hours monitoring of the child. An overall architecture diagram of the proposed system can be seen in Fig. 1. On the left hand side the two cases of patient monitoring are displayed; while on the right hand side the doctors and the access to the system are displayed.

A. In-house case

During this case,(a UML diagram describing the actions sequence for this case can be seen in Fig. 2) a sensor network is installed in the child’s house that will be used in

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the in-house wireless sensor network © IEEE 2007 [6]

order to continuously monitor ECG signals from the patient [6] – [10]. Several other environmental parameters like light, temperature, sound, acceleration are also monitored so as to continuously check the living conditions. The ECG (3 lead) signal is recorded by a sensor carried from the child, that is part of a wireless sensor network (WSN) installed in the house. The ECG sensor has been specially designed & developed by SignalGenerix Ltd (<http://www.signalgenerix.com>) [7]. Signal information from the wearable sensor is propagated to a local monitoring station which will also act as a gateway to the rest of the monitoring network. The cardiac pulse is propagated through the WSN to the local monitoring station with an embedded broadcast algorithm.

The local monitoring station is responsible for collecting environmental measurements (e.g. temperature, 2D accelerometer, sound, light):

- Sample the ECG signal.
- Store the sensor data locally.
- Analyze the ECG signal in order to detect possible cardiac arrhythmias.

In the case of a detected arrhythmia:

- Send an alarm message to the central monitoring station (located in hospital), to the supervising doctor and a relative.

For our case we have chosen to develop a Mote-based sensor network based on Crossbow® equipment [10], [11], [12]. The proposed network that will be used to cover the patient’s house is based on motes like MicaZ™ while the acquisition of ECG data is performed through a custom

Fig.4 Results for 10000 packets sent

created board connected to the MDA300CA™ acquisition board. Additional environmental data will be collected through the MTS310CA™ sensor board. All collected information will be transmitted to a gateway, MIB510™ connected on a Personal Computer; this is going to be the local monitoring system(see Fig.4).

B. Moving patient case

The second case is more general and will be used in order to complete the coverage of the system. For this case, the child is monitored using the same ECG recording device (Fig. 3) but the signals are transmitted, through a PDA, directly to the central monitoring system (for the test pilot case an HP iPAQ hw6915 was used). The transmission is performed through the use of 2.5G and 3G mobile communication networks (GPRS/UMTS) [1]. Details for this case, as well as for the ECG acquisition device, have already been presented in [7].

C. Central Monitoring Station

For both cases data are transmitted to a central monitoring station (see Fig. 1); where this station is responsible to:

- Store data sent from the local monitoring station.
- Display data transmitted from the local monitoring stations and through a web interface.
- Analyze the ECG signal further (based on open source arrhythmia det. Algorithm [13]) send a message (SMS, e-mail etc.) to the doctor [7].

III. RESULTS

Several tests were performed in order to verify the correct transmission of data over the system. The tests described here are for the in-house use of the system. Tests

were performed using the ECG simulator with a sensor node connected to the gateway [7]. Initial tests were performed using omni-directional antennas for the sensor nodes (provided with Crossbow nodes). Tests were performed to ensure the correct functionality of the system using two repeaters, and positioning the sensors at various distances from each other, including various obstructions between them. Examples of these experiments showed that the greater the distances, the bigger the packet loss (that was somehow expected), but bigger loss was observed when there were more obstructions (for instance, when the two sensors were in different rooms, and the doors connecting the rooms were closed) [7].

Following the tests with omni directional antennas. The idea of using directional antennas came up since the antennas we chose were not initially designed for our application. The new directional antennas were designed by SignalGenerix LTD, it is very small, and limits power consumption on the nodes. Power consumption is not our concern however, because we chose to test the directional antennas only on the central gateway and the repeaters. It made no sense testing a directional antenna on the patient's node, as the patient will be moving and have no constant direction, not harnessing the good effects of the directional antenna we wanted to.

The antennas, were based on the Yagi-Uda architecture. Using fractal geometry the size of the antenna was reduced to a small printed circuit, having a gain of 6.2dBs, and a very low cost.

For the tests, we used our CardioBee device, the device that collects and sends the ECG from the patient, an ECG simulator, one gateway, the original omni-directional antenna and the new directional printed antenna. We wanted to compare the packet loss rate and retransmission rate regarding some variables: Distance, obstacles, interference from other applications utilizing the same frequencies as 802.15.4 does in the ISM band and whether the patient is stationary or moving. We tried to eliminate other factors that could affect our results (for instance, new batteries were used for each test although, in the long run, did not affected anything). All the tests were done indoor, with no Wireless Access points turned on.

Tests done:

- Base and stationary patient had 3m distance
- Base and stationary patient had 5m distance.
- Base and stationary patient had 10m distance.
- Base and stationary patient had 5m distance and a closed door between.
- Base and stationary patient had 10m distance and a closed door between.
- Base and stationary patient had 10m distance and two closed doors between.

All the aforementioned tests were repeated with the directional antenna installed on the base.

Figure 4 shows the results for all tests for 10000 packets sent (tests were repeated multiple times, the above values are the average values). The results were as expected, with the worst case being the one with the largest distance and obstacles for both antennas. Table 1 shows the loss rates for the several tests that were carried out and the comparison of the initial to the new setup.

Table 1. Loss and Retransmission rate values for the in-house patient case tests

Test	Loss Rate	Retrans. rate
3m omni	0.13%	1.09%
5m omni	0.19%	2.42%
5m omni door	0.32%	3.04%
10m omni	0.85%	10.89%
10m omni door	1.08%	13.23%
10m omni 2 doors	1.23%	18.93%
3m yagi	0	0.01%
5m yagi	0	0.09%
5m yagi door	0	0.12%
10m yagi	0	0.75%
10m yagi door	0	0.89%
10m yagi 2 doors	0	1.54%
Omni – moving patient	20.15%	193.91%
Directional – moving patient	4.68%	63.12%

Although the results show that the directional offers less loss rate and retransmission rate for a stationary patient, in a real life scenario, the patient is not going to be stationary. We needed to see how the rates would change if the patient was moving. So, we had the base receiving packets, while the patient was moving randomly and constantly, within a range of 2 to 10 meters from the base (see last two rows of Table 1).

All the tests showed that the directional antennas offer less loss and retransmission rates, with minimal additional cost and with no extra changes in the infrastructure of the system needed.

The positions of the repeaters and the base must always be considered for each house independently, since avoiding obstacles is essential to achieve minimal loss rates, and obstacles are different in every house.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Concluding, a prototype m-Health system for monitoring children with possible arrhythmias was developed, implemented, and tested. It is anticipated that through the use of the proposed system we will be able to help the pediatric cardiologist in the identification of arrhythmia, thus helping the physician prescribe a proper treatment. We have provided the architecture description and all the hardware tests for the system. Future work will cover the complete live testing of the system with all actors (healthy subjects, patients, doctors, and parents) involved, in order to ensure the flawless functionality and robustness of the system.

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